

N3C Query Report:

Vaccination

Abstract

This query examines the effect of vaccination (prior to COVID-19 infection) on the risk of PASC. When considering patients across all sites we see a modest protective effect of vaccination on PASC with an odds ratio of 0.81 (0.79, 0.83). Limiting to sites with more reliable vaccination information yields an odds ratio of 0.95 (0.91, 0.99). The sensitivity of the effect to which sites are included suggests the presence of potential confounding factors at the site level.

Methods

Inclusion criteria

- **Study period:** 3/1/2020 – 4/30/2022
- **Age:** Any age
- **COVID-19 positive:** via a qualifying index event between 3/1/2020 – 4/30/2022
 - Definition 1. Positive SARS-CoV-2 PCR test (no antibody tests)
 - Definition 2. Diagnosis of COVID-19 via 1 inpatient or 2 outpatient instances of ICD-10 code U07.1
- **Pre-COVID utilization:** 2 or more visits with the healthcare system within the year before the index event
- **Post-COVID utilization:** 1 or more visits with the healthcare system at least 120 days after the index event

Data was released on June 23, 2022 in release version 82 of the N3C data enclave. Nine of 74 sites were removed due to having any one of the following data quality concerns: (1) a date shift of more than 30 days, (2) serum creatinine and lymphocyte count results available in less than 25% of hospitalizations, or (3) more than 10% of hospitalizations starting more than 200 days after the COVID-19 index date.

Definitions

Index event

The earliest instance of COVID-19 positivity between 3/1/2020 – 4/30/2022. A patient's first COVID positivity is defined by either Definition 1 or 2 above (lab-based or diagnosis-based).

Diagnosis of PASC

PASC was defined as previously described¹, trained on a cohort of patients who were known to have a u09.9 diagnosis. For the purpose of this report, the model was retrained without the use of vaccination status as a predictor. In order to label a patient as having PASC or not, the patient must meet the following criteria: (1) they must be at least 18 years old, (2) they must have at least 2 days of data in the system, (3) they must have at least one diagnosis and one medication in the pre- or post-index period, and (4) they must have data at least 90 days since the covid index. Approximately 30% of patients meeting the inclusion criteria do not have sufficient data to determine if they have PASC.

Cell size and patient privacy protection

In order to comply with N3C data use policies, any cell sizes under 20 were suppressed and the surrounding row and column data were adjusted with small gaussian noise in order to obfuscate the suppressed counts.

mRNA Vaccine

COVID-19 vaccines manufactured by Moderna or Pfizer and administered prior to a patient's COVID-19 index date.

Non-mRNA Vaccine

COVID-19 vaccines manufactured by Johnson & Johnson or Astrazeneca and administered prior to a patient's COVID-19 index date.

High Quality Vaccination Sites

There is no reliable and widely-used observation in the N3C data enclave that notes when a patient is not vaccinated. An absence of vaccination records is a better indicator of non-vaccination at some sites than others, given that sites vary in how complete their vaccine records are. We calculated two site-specific statistics to determine which sites offer the most reliable population of unvaccinated individuals: (1) the **observed proportion** of 12+ years old individuals with a recorded vaccination and (2) the **expected proportion** of 12+ years old individuals with a vaccine according to CDC reports for vaccination rates in patients' home counties. A ratio of observed over expected proportions yields a vaccine coverage ratio. Nine out of the 65 included sites have a vaccine coverage ratio of at least $\frac{2}{3}$, which are designated as high quality vaccination sites.

Results

Out of 4,542,466 patients in the N3C enclave with a qualifying COVID index event at one of the included 65 sites, 1,668,314 meet the remaining utilization criteria. A total of 95,984 patients were classified as having had PASC and 1,086,475 were designated as not having had PASC. No PASC classification was made for 485,623 patients.

The cohort is 61% female with an average age of 44. Only 9.9% of patients had a reported vaccination prior to getting COVID, in large part because many patients were infected before vaccinations became available. Pfizer is the most common vaccine manufacturer, used by 67% of those with a reported vaccination. Moderna is the next most common at 27%, meaning that the mRNA-derived vaccines make up the vast majority (94%) of reported vaccines. The remainder of the vaccines can be attributed to Johnson & Johnson, with the exception of a very small number of Astrazeneca vaccines.

Age is a clear risk factor for PASC: 13% of PASC patients are below the age of 36 compared to 28% of patients without a PASC classification. Meanwhile, 26% of PASC patients are over 65 years old compared to 20% of non-PASC patients. Black or African American non-Hispanic patients have higher-than-average rates of PASC, while rates for White non-Hispanic patients are lower-than-average.

Table 1 summarizes the demographic characteristics and vaccination statuses of the COVID-19 positive patients across 65 sites.

Table 1. COVID-19 Positive Patient Characteristics, All Sites

Characteristic	Overall # (%)	With PASC # (%)	Without PASC # (%)	No PASC Classification # (%)
Age groups				
Mean	44	54	49	31
<1	16619 (1.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	16619 (3.4)
01-04	39598 (2.4)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	39598 (8.2)
05-09	44765 (2.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	44765 (9.2)
10-15	72871 (4.4)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	72871 (15.0)
16-20	97945 (5.9)	1066 (1.1)	55163 (5.1)	41716 (8.6)
21-35	344757 (20.7)	11382 (11.9)	253551 (23.3)	79824 (16.4)
36-45	241728 (14.5)	17282 (18.0)	173961 (16.0)	50485 (10.4)
46-55	259812 (15.6)	20362 (21.2)	190476 (17.5)	48974 (10.1)
56-65	257966 (15.5)	20975 (21.9)	192611 (17.7)	44380 (9.1)
66+	290298 (17.4)	24916 (26.0)	220633 (20.3)	44749 (9.2)
unknown	1955 (0.1)	<20 (-)	80 (0.0)	1874 (0.4)
Sex				
Male	649764 (38.9)	30669 (32.0)	407066 (37.5)	212029 (43.6)
Female	1018124 (61.0)	65303 (68.0)	679227 (62.5)	273594 (56.3)
Other/Unknown	426 (0.0)	<20 (-)	182 (0.0)	232 (0.0)
Race Ethnicity				

Characteristic	Overall # (%)	With PASC # (%)	Without PASC # (%)	No PASC Classification # (%)
White Non-Hispanic	1090309 (65.4)	60926 (63.5)	730371 (67.2)	299012 (61.5)
Black or African American Non-Hispanic	220791 (13.2)	16398 (17.1)	140769 (13.0)	63624 (13.1)
Hispanic or Latino Any Race	207880 (12.5)	11286 (11.8)	124556 (11.5)	72038 (14.8)
Unknown	86262 (5.2)	4609 (4.8)	54995 (5)	26658 (5.5)
Asian Non-Hispanic	39015 (2.3)	2078 (2.2)	24387 (2.2)	12550 (2.6)
Other Non-Hispanic	24057 (1.4)	687 (0.7)	11397 (1.0)	11973 (2.5)
Pre-COVID Vaccination				
Mean Doses Documented	0.19	0.13	0.16	0.26
Any Vaccination Documented	164884 (9.9)	6822 (7.1)	95773 (8.8)	62289 (12.8)
0	1503430 (90.1)	89162 (92.9)	990702 (91.2)	423566 (87.2)
1	38796 (2.3)	1931 (2.0)	24768 (2.3)	12097 (2.5)
2	105037 (6.3)	4491 (4.7)	65645 (6.0)	34901 (7.2)
3	20243 (1.2)	373 (0.4)	4996 (0.5)	14874 (3.1)
4+	808 (0.0)	27 (0.0)	364 (0.0)	417 (0.1)
Vaccine Type				
Any mRNA	154860 (9.3)	6366 (6.6)	89134 (8.2)	59360 (12.2)
Any Non-mRNA	10355 (0.6)	450 (0.5)	6657 (0.6)	3248 (0.7)
Both mRNA and Non-mRNA	593 (0.0)	<20 (-)	156 (0.0)	425 (0.1)
Vaccine Manufacturer				

Characteristic	Overall # (%)	With PASC # (%)	Without PASC # (%)	No PASC Classification # (%)
Any Pfizer	110213 (6.6)	4488 (4.7)	62504 (5.8)	43221 (8.9)
Any Moderna	45799 (2.7)	1915 (2.0)	27061 (2.5)	16823 (3.5)
Any Johnson & Johnson	10340 (0.6)	450 (0.5)	6652 (0.6)	3238 (0.7)
Any Other Manufacturer	2157 (0.1)	125 (0.1)	1169 (0.1)	863 (0.2)

Table 2 summarizes vaccination counts and PASC risk. The column *Vaccinated After COVID* refers to the number of patients in the given row that received a vaccination after their COVID-19 index date. All odds ratios are calculated in comparison to having no recorded vaccine doses.

Table 2. Risk by Type and Doses, All Sites

Characteristic	Overall # (%)	With PASC # (%)	Without PASC # (%)	Risk of PASC Odds Ratio (95% CI)	Vaccinated After COVID # (%)
Any Vaccine Type					
No Recorded Doses	1079864 (91.3)	89162 (92.9)	990702 (91.2)	1	374304 (87.7)
Any Doses	102595 (8.7)	6822 (7.1)	95773 (8.8)	0.81 (0.79, 0.83)	52569 (12.3)
1 Dose	26699 (2.3)	1931 (2.0)	24768 (2.3)	0.88 (0.84, 0.92)	17146 (4.0)
2 Doses	70136 (5.9)	4491 (4.7)	65645 (6.0)	0.78 (0.75, 0.8)	34136 (8.0)
3 Doses	5369 (0.5)	373 (0.4)	4996 (0.5)	0.84 (0.76, 0.93)	1088 (0.3)
4+ Doses	391 (0.0)	27 (0.0)	364 (0.0)	0.84 (0.57, 1.24)	199 (0.0)
mRNA Vaccine					
Any Doses	95500 (8.1)	6366 (6.6)	89134 (8.2)	0.81 (0.79, 0.83)	49806 (11.7)
1 Dose	20952 (1.8)	1597 (1.7)	19355 (1.8)	0.92 (0.88, 0.97)	14822 (3.5)
2 Doses	68942 (5.8)	4385 (4.6)	64557 (5.9)	0.77 (0.75, 0.79)	33748 (7.9)
3 Doses	5232 (0.4)	357 (0.4)	4875 (0.4)	0.83 (0.74, 0.92)	1045 (0.2)
4+ Doses	374 (0.0)	27 (0.0)	347 (0.0)	0.87 (0.59, 1.29)	191 (0.0)
Non-mRNA Vaccine					
Any Doses	7107 (0.6)	442 (0.5)	6657 (0.6)	0.75 (0.68, 0.83)	2738 (0.6)
1 Dose	6957 (0.6)	440 (0.5)	6517 (0.6)	0.77 (0.7, 0.84)	2702 (0.6)
2 Doses	150 (0.0)	<20 (-)	140 (0.0)	0.16 (0.04, 0.65)	36 (0.0)
3 Doses	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	-	0 (0.0)

4+ Doses	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	-	0 (0.0)
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Table 3 is identical in structure to Table 1, but only includes patients from the high quality vaccination sites.

Table 3. COVID-19 Positive Patient Characteristics, High Quality Vaccination Sites

Characteristic	Overall # (%)	With PASC # (%)	Without PASC # (%)	No PASC Classification # (%)
Age groups				
Mean	43	52	48	30
<1	5250 (0.7)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	5250 (2.4)
01-04	13349 (1.9)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	13349 (6.0)
05-09	18698 (2.6)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	18698 (8.5)
10-15	34205 (4.8)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	34205 (15.5)
16-20	52263 (7.3)	283 (1.2)	27111 (5.8)	24869 (11.3)
21-35	158822 (22.3)	2905 (12.7)	113359 (24.2)	42558 (19.3)
36-45	106341 (14.9)	4878 (21.3)	77326 (16.5)	24137 (10.9)
46-55	110245 (15.5)	5146 (22.5)	82410 (17.6)	22689 (10.3)
56-65	103021 (14.5)	4759 (20.8)	79306 (16.9)	18956 (8.6)
66+	109339 (15.4)	4894 (21.4)	88372 (18.9)	16073 (7.3)
unknown	86 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	56 (0.0)	30 (0.0)
Sex				
Male	268952 (37.8)	6706 (29.3)	165506 (35.4)	96740 (43.8)
Female	442361 (62.2)	16157 (70.7)	302323 (64.6)	123881 (56.1)
Other/Unknown	306 (0.0)	<20 (-)	111 (0.0)	193 (0.1)
Race Ethnicity				
White Non-Hispanic	504615 (70.9)	15072 (65.9)	339362 (72.5)	150181 (68.0)

Characteristic	Overall # (%)	With PASC # (%)	Without PASC # (%)	No PASC Classification # (%)
Black or African American Non-Hispanic	76252 (10.7)	3257 (14.2)	52255 (11.2)	20740 (9.4)
Hispanic or Latino Any Race	92345 (13.0)	3420 (15.0)	55441 (11.8)	33484 (15.2)
Unknown	7295 (1.0)	347 (1.5)	4094 (0.9)	2854 (1.3)
Asian Non-Hispanic	14301 (2.0)	502 (2.2)	8851 (1.9)	4948 (2.2)
Other Non-Hispanic	16811 (2.4)	267 (1.2)	7937 (1.7)	8607 (3.9)
Pre-COVID Vaccination				
Mean Doses Documented	0.22	0.20	0.21	0.22
Any Vaccination Documented	83576 (11.7)	2557 (11.2)	56126 (12.0)	24893 (11.3)
0	628043 (88.3)	20308 (88.8)	411814 (88.0)	195921 (88.7)
1	21100 (3.0)	745 (3.3)	15095 (3.2)	5260 (2.4)
2	55014 (7.7)	1676 (7.3)	38247 (8.2)	15091 (6.8)
3	7014 (1.0)	126 (0.6)	2515 (0.5)	4373 (2.0)
4+	448 (0.1)	<20 (-)	269 (0.1)	169 (0.1)
Vaccine Type				
Any mRNA	77195 (10.8)	2342 (10.2)	51506 (11.0)	23347 (10.6)
Any Non-mRNA	6616 (0.9)	214 (0.9)	4687 (1.0)	1715 (0.8)
Both mRNA and Non-mRNA	302 (0.0)	<20 (-)	100 (0.0)	195 (0.1)
Vaccine Manufacturer				
Any Pfizer	49204 (6.9)	1456 (6.4)	32886 (7.0)	14862 (6.7)
Any Moderna	28654 (4.0)	905 (4.0)	18930 (4.0)	8819 (4.0)
Any Johnson & Johnson	6607 (0.9)	214 (0.9)	4684 (1.0)	1709 (0.8)

Characteristic	Overall # (%)	With PASC # (%)	Without PASC # (%)	No PASC Classification # (%)
Any Other Manufacturer	157 (0.0)	<20 (-)	81 (0.0)	65 (0.0)

Table 4 is identical in structure to Table 2, but only includes patients from the high quality vaccination sites.

Table 4. Risk by Type and Doses, High Quality Vaccination Sites

Characteristic	Overall # (%)	With PASC # (%)	Without PASC # (%)	Risk of PASC Odds Ratio (95% CI)	Vaccinated After COVID # (%)
Any Vaccine Type					
No Recorded Doses	628043 (88.3)	20308 (88.8)	411814 (88.0)	1	324812 (88.4)
Any Doses	83598 (11.7)	2557 (11.2)	56126 (12)	0.95 (0.91, 0.99)	42532 (11.6)
1 Dose	21100 (3.0)	745 (3.3)	15095 (3.2)	1.09 (1.01, 1.18)	14182 (3.9)
2 Doses	55014 (7.7)	1676 (7.3)	38247 (8.2)	0.94 (0.9, 0.99)	26883 (7.3)
3 Doses	7014 (1.0)	126 (0.6)	2515 (0.5)	0.56 (0.46, 0.66)	1276 (0.3)
4+ Doses	448 (0.1)	<20 (-)	269 (0.1)	0.66 (0.35, 1.24)	191 (0.1)
mRNA Vaccine					
Any Doses	77195 (10.8)	2346 (10.3)	51506 (11)	0.94 (0.9, 0.98)	40030 (10.9)
1 Dose	15219 (2.1)	545 (2.4)	10656 (2.3)	1.11 (1.01, 1.21)	11812 (3.2)
2 Doses	54619 (7.7)	1664 (7.3)	38114 (8.1)	0.94 (0.9, 0.99)	26792 (7.3)
3 Doses	6922 (1.0)	123 (0.5)	2473 (0.5)	0.55 (0.46, 0.66)	1242 (0.3)
4+ Doses	435 (0.1)	<20 (-)	263 (0.1)	1 (0.58, 1.7)	184 (0.1)
Non-mRNA Vaccine					
Any Doses	6616 (0.9)	212 (0.9)	4687 (1)	0.99 (0.86, 1.14)	2550 (0.7)
1 Dose	6423 (0.9)	211 (0.9)	4610 (1.0)	1.02 (0.88, 1.17)	2504 (0.7)
2 Doses	193 (0.0)	<20 (-)	77 (0.0)	0.16 (0.02, 1.15)	46 (0.0)
3 Doses	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	-	0 (0.0)
4+ Doses	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	-	0 (0.0)

Discussion

The results in Table 2 suggest a modest protective effect of vaccination in preventing PASC, with an odds ratio of 0.81 (0.79, 0.83) for those who received at least a single vaccination prior to COVID onset. Those who received two doses were slightly more protected with an odds ratio of 0.78 (0.75, 0.79). We see no significant difference between mRNA and non-mRNA vaccinations in their capacity to reduce the risk of PASC.

The results from Table 2 are tempered by those from Table 4, which show much weaker protective effects of vaccination. Receiving one or two vaccinations elicit odds ratios of 1.09 (1.01, 1.18) and 0.94 (0.90, 0.99), respectively. This difference from Table 2 is counter-intuitive—we might expect that Table 4, which includes only sites with more reliable vaccination information, would show a more robust effect.

The sensitivity of the result to which sites are included suggests that significant confounders could be contributing to the results reported herein. Many sites report no or very few vaccination records and the majority of sites have a vaccine coverage ratio (see definition of High Quality Vaccination Sites) of below 0.5. If sites with higher vaccination rates also serve higher risk populations, or if they more consistently report conditions consistent with PASC, then we would expect Table 2 to overstate the protective effects of vaccination.

Tables 2 and 4 are consistent in their characterization of those who were vaccinated following their COVID-19 index date. In both tables, 88% of those who received any vaccinations after their COVID-19 index date were unvaccinated at the time of COVID. The effect of post-COVID vaccination is not in the scope of this study, but represents another potential confounding effect.

Limitations

Only vaccinations reported to (or learned by) an N3C site would be included in the study, so the number, timing, and types of SARS-CoV-2 vaccinations reported may not accurately reflect the complete vaccination status of the patient. The current study utilizes our pre-existing machine learning model for PASC classifications which continues to evolve as additional data, including usage of the U09.9 ICD-10 diagnostic code for post-COVID conditions, are incorporated into the model. Additionally, our current PASC computational model does not calculate PASC classifications for patients under the age of 18, which prevents the investigation of PASC-related questions for that patient population.

As mentioned in the Discussion, there are significant potential confounders between vaccination and PASC that are not explored in this study. In particular, sites vary widely in their rates of both vaccination and PASC. It is likely that some sites with artificially low rates of vaccination have fundamentally different patient populations than those with more accurate rates of vaccination.

Appendix

References

- 1 Pfaff ER, Girvin AT, Bennett TD, Bhatia A, Brooks IM, Deer RR, *et al.* Who has long-COVID? A big data approach n.d. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.10.18.21265168>.